

CHALLENGES AND TRENDS SHAPING THE POST-PANDEMIC AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Purpose – *This work aims to identify emerging challenges and opportunities of the automotive sector as a result of the COVID-19 outbreak. With shortages starting to arise even before the pandemic, the automotive industry was one of the most affected during the pandemic. OEMs and suppliers must not overcome these challenges and grasp new opportunities to satisfy the new demands of their customers.*

Methodology/approach – *In order to understand the development of challenges from the pre-pandemic industry to the post-pandemic one, financial and industry related reports published by major consulting entities have been gathered and reviewed. Major challenges and opportunities have been selected and further highlighted throughout the conduct of this paper.*

Findings – *If the automotive chip shortage and sudden drop of vehicle orders are a clear sign of a struggling industry during the COVID-19 pandemic, the rapidly changing behavior of the road users is now the hardest to satisfy. Switching from conventional vehicle ownership to subscription services, customers are now asking for more transparency and started searching for easier process while acquiring a vehicle. On the other hand, the rapidly evolving technology of the automotive industry and a vehicle's connected interfaces, cybersecurity becomes a concern of the industry that needs to be addressed.*

Research limitations – *The uncertainty of the actual pandemic evolution is affecting the accuracy of the conducted study as the predictions might anytime be obsolete. However, reports conducted throughout the whole pandemic development have been analyzed and the combined predictions are presented in this work.*

Originality/value – *This paper analyses numerous reports released by well-established consultancy firms, bringing together prediction published in the last three years. Therefore, a complete overview of the challenges evolution through the pandemic as well as a stable vision for 2030 are presented.*

Key words: *automotive, management, challenges*

Introduction

Everyday life came to a complete stop in several countries around the globe as the COVID-19 outbreak has been declared a pandemic. This event has caused several automotive businesses to close or scale back operations, this leading to severe economic impact for the industry [Hausler et al. (2020)]. With long lasting negative impact on the mobility, the already hardly the automotive OEMs and suppliers are now struggling with changing customer demand and more complex cybersecurity attack. However, industrial challenges, changes in customer demands and their inquisitiveness towards new trends may vary from one region to another [Vitale et al. (2020)]. Now, OEMs must persuade their consumers back to the new vehicle market even if the interest in conventional vehicle ownership has fallen throughout the years [Vitale et al. (2020)]. New services must now be implemented as it is foreseen that services will account for 30% of the total revenues of OEMs by 2030 [Accenture (202)]. Therefore, choosing the correct services to offer and allocating the necessary development resources, are key factors in determining the future market leaders of the automotive industry. With so many emerging trends, the automotive industry faces as many challenges as opportunities. During the conduct of this paper, a few of these are to be further addressed. Recently emerged topics of the automotive industry such as customer behavior changes and cybersecurity vulnerabilities are described. Moreover, the well-known shortage of vehicle semiconductors together with an industry's forecast for 2030 are topics highlighted throughout the paper.

Vehicle subscription services

To diversify their revenue streams, car manufacturers have been seeking for alternative business models for a long time already. While car sharing, ride hailing, and other transportation services, have grown in popularity, there have only been two real alternatives to traditional vehicle ownership: short-term rental or leasing. Both services are either not cheap for the consumer, impose long-term commitments or enforce restrictive terms. It was only a matter of time until OEMs and other major players of the automotive industry would have introduced subscription services. In addition, numerous startups have joined the game in Europe where the market has been proven to bring the biggest revenues. Therefore, the vehicle subscriptions market could potentially grow into a \$30 billion to \$40 billion market during the next decade [Schellong et al. (2021)].

Public transport and shared mobility have been brought suddenly to a near halt, with consumers looking for alternative, safer methods of travel. Seeking the safety of private vehicles, consumers began to be more interested in purchasing or in having available a private method of travel. Being asked if the pandemic had an impact on their decision of acquiring a vehicle in order to avoid public transport, 44% of the Romanian responders have answered affirmatively. On the other hand, the same study conducted by Deloitte shows that less than 20% of the Austrian and Belgian responders have the same opinion [Proff et al. (2022)]. The pandemic, however, is not the only key driver in changing the desire of consumers of having an own vehicle. The tedious car buying process, residual value loss and lack of price transparency are the main reasons why consumers are gaining interest in vehicle subscription services [Schellong et al. (2021)]. Consumers regard subscription services as being more accessible and less risky than the tradition vehicle ownership. With higher prices of vehicle purchases caused by component shortage and increase in cost of raw materials, subscription services will grow in popularity. New companies emerge on the market with attractive Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) having numerous features but without having a brand history behind such as other big, well-established OEMs. With subscription services now available, consumers are more willing in trying these vehicles as these services are mitigation one's ownerships risks such as high battery replacement costs which can cost up to \$16,000 [Schellong et al. (2021)].

Subscription services are not foreseen to overtake the traditional car ownership anytime soon. As Netflix did not overtake Universal Studios, nor did Spotify catch up with Warner Bros., vehicle subscriptions are expected to only gain a certain pool of customers [Schellong et al. (2021)]. However, starting with 2022, it can be clearly seen that more and more consumers are willing to use services like short-term leasing and subscription models because they began to revalue having a continual access to a private vehicle. [Heineke et al. (2021)]. Slowly, more consumers will be more opened to switching from a traditionally owned vehicle to a shared mobility service. Even if such services are nowadays a small niche of the automotive industry, as previously stated, the market growth is expected to reach high levels in the upcoming decade [Heineke et al. (2020)].

Auto-semiconductor shortage

It can be clearly stated that the semiconductor shortage has not been caused by a single occurrence or disruption, but by a series of related incidents. Being affected by the COVID-19 outbreak, the automotive industry has felt a massive drop in vehicle orders even since the beginning of the pandemic [Burkacky et al. (2021)]. However, the semiconductor shortage began to create difficulties in other various industries too when manufacturing lines of electronics have been slowed down. Even so, the effects in the automotive industry have been more severe than in the electronics one [Burkacky et al. (2022)]. This crisis has rapidly demonstrated the weakness of the semiconductors supply chain that was heavily depending on the only major semiconductor production center, Asia. OEMs and their suppliers are currently operating in a crisis mode, being now forced to address the imbalance in demand [Burkacky et al. (2021)].

With a 179% increase in semiconductor manufacturing capacity since 2000 and a roughly 4% annual increase, the semiconductor manufacturers are not coping with the high demand requested by the automotive industry. This demand is strongly underlined by the semiconductor utilization over 80% in the last decade. Having the utilization in 2020 at almost 90% can be easily regarded as full utilization, further affecting the lead timed in the automotive industry [Burkacky et al. (2021)]. On the other hand, the geopolitical tensions are now causing further disruption even in a post-pandemic word. This uncertainty has led some electronic manufacturers to significantly expand their chip inventories in order to survive a possible next semiconductor shortage. These geopolitical uncertainties have been added

on top of the already existing crisis because Russia provides more than 30% of the global need of palladium while Ukraine provides more than 40% of the global semiconductor-grade [Burkacky et al. (2022)]. Another issue is strongly related to logistics, as the big majority of semiconductors are transported by air, where shipping rates have climbed dramatically to new records. At the same time, the air transport capacity has also dropped. All industries still face a major gap between their demand and the actual chip supply, even after two years since the beginning of the chip shortage crisis. Sales in all industries have recovered faster and with higher volumes than anticipated by experts during the pandemic. This creating further drawbacks in the supply chain [Burkacky et al. (2022)]. Consumer demand has also switched during the COVID-19 outbreak, focusing on high-tech devices highly needed in a home office layout. Routers, modems, laptops, and PC manufacturing demand rapidly increased therefore more semiconductors were needed. Therefore, vehicle manufacturers and their supplier are facing yet another challenge, competition in semiconductors with other sectors. This challenge has highlighted the need of reducing the industry's dependency of Asian suppliers.

Cybersecurity challenges

Cutting edge technologies of the automotive industry such as autonomous driving are a vulnerable target of cybersecurity attacks. The related 5G technology which allows connected driving is transforming modern vehicles in information hubs as large amount of data must be transferred in order for these technologies to function. The lack of cybersecurity requirements in the automotive industry and during the product development process, has demonstrated that connected vehicles are an easy target for black hat hackers [Brown et al. (2021)]. Therefore, new regulations, standards and frameworks focusing on the cybersecurity aspect of the automotive industry have been recently published or are under development. With WP.29 regulation developed by the World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulation already published, more than 60 automotive markets are requiring evidence of cybersecurity practices in the rigorous type-approval process [Heineke et al. (2021)]. Being now obliged to integrate cybersecurity in their internal processes, OEMs and their suppliers will be able to respond in a timely manner to various cybersecurity incidents. The WP.29 regulation consists of R155 and R156, where R155 imposes the development of a Cybersecurity Management system while R156 addresses the post-manufacturing aspect of the software together with the OTA update procedures [Levy (2022)]. Supporting the two previously mentioned regulations, ISO/SAE 21434 provides a methodology for OEM and their suppliers for calculating the risk score of an identified asset and therefore to classify and prioritize based on vulnerability analysis. A new acronym has rapidly gained importance in the automotive industry, TARA. The threat analysis and risk management is defined by the released standards and aids manufacturers to assess how much a road user might be impacted by a possible vulnerabilities. This risk and threat evaluation must be conducted throughout the whole lifecycle of a vehicle [Levy (2022)].

Cybersecurity is regarded as a continuously developing challenge as the number of global connected vehicles will grow from 330 million units in 2018 to 775 million units in 2023 [Levy (2022)]. At the same time, when compared to 2018, an increase of 225% in the cybersecurity incident numbers can be seen in 2021 [Levy (2022)]. Not only the number of attacks has risen during the years but also the complexity of the attacks and the attack vectors. The automotive industry, as well as municipal authorities, faced challenges in 2021 due to the complex and sophisticated cybersecurity attacks. They tried to identify cybersecurity solutions against all current and future attack vectors. It is yet unclear whether newly published standards and regulations will limit the black-hat hackers or encourage them to create more complex attack techniques. Also in 2021, black-hat hackers accounted for almost 57% of the identified attacks while only 40% have been conducted by whit-hat hackers aiming to identify vulnerabilities and to improve the cybersecurity aspect of the industry. No segment of the automotive industry is nowadays clear from cybersecurity attacks and involved threats. Not even newly concepts such as subscription services or EV which can be impacted by vulnerabilities of the charging infrastructure [Levy (2022)]. The rapidly growing demand of electric vehicle charging stations, cybersecurity threats have been neglected. Various security flaws have been discovered by white-hat hackers, from infiltrating home networks to disabling charging ports or even removing the owner's access to the vehicle [Levy (2022)].

With arising number of cybersecurity attacks registered by automotive manufacturers, OEMs are now required to implement proper cybersecurity management procedures during product development, manufacturing process as well as during the post-production lifetime of the product. OTA updates must now also focus on mitigating continuously monitored cybersecurity risks. A successful company will now be characterized by a strong organizational risk management strategy including risk identification, risk mitigation and risk monitoring [Brown et al. (2021)].

Vision 2030

It is believed that four major trends will shape the automotive industry in the current decade. Changing revenue streams and marketplaces, consumer mobility behavior modification, spread of cutting-edge technology, and complex cooperation and competition are the trends that will modify the traditional automotive market [Kaas et al. (2016)]. At the same time, it is widely believed by experts that the automotive industry is ripe for disruption. The industry will look completely different in the next decade as well-established models such as the implemented just in time model must be now reanalyzed because of the component and raw material shortages.

The already changing revenue streams of the automotive industry will expand to data-driven services and on-demand mobility [Kaas et al. (2016)]. Until the end of this decade, it is believed that this will increase the industry revenue with 30%, an additional 1.5 trillion USD, accelerating the yearly industry growth to 4.4%. Passenger vehicles are rapidly becoming a method for drivers and passengers to spend their commute time for personal pursuits, include new offered services and media entertainment. Due to the growing interest towards shared mobility, the vehicle unit sales will annually increase at a lower rate than before. Predicting that the sales will have an annual growth of 2% in the current decade, comparing to the 3.6% growth that the marked was used to in the last five years [Kaas et al. (2016)]. On the other hand, to reach the plan of switching to EVs, the first major barrier must be overcome. The lack of charging infrastructure is the main fear of consumers when it comes to “range anxiety” and adoption of the new EV concept [Brown et al. (2021)]. Another big challenge for the European automotive sector is to assure supply chain resilience for critical raw material (CRM) [Brown et al. (2021)]. Without clear solutions, the CRM shortage will drastically impact the European OEMs. The nowadays dependency on Chinese and Taiwanese suppliers has already been proven to be a stress test for the European industry. However, improvements in the Li-ion battery supply can already be seen with more factories opening in the EU [Brown et al. (2021)].

To keep the share of the automotive market, OEMs must now change their strategy from providing “hardware” to providing integrated mobility services [Kaas et al. (2016)]. At the same time, the importance of B2B sales is highlighted by the rapidly evolving shared mobility service providers, obliging OEMs to also focus on their new business customers. Therefore, the automotive industry must nowadays face many challenges but at the same time, it provides a large variety of diversification opportunities for conventional OEMs to survive the continuously evolving and demanding automotive sector.

Conclusions

The automotive industry still faces challenges that have started even before the COVID-19 outbreak. In addition, the geopolitical tensions and pandemic related shortages will continue to have a big negative impact on the industry's future. Some automotive manufacturers and supplier have proven through the implementation of lessons learned during the last decade's recession that they have found themselves in a better financial position during the pandemic than others [Vitale et al. (2020)]. Even with the arising opportunities, it is anticipated that the passenger vehicle manufacturing capacity utilization will stay below 75% until 2027 [Vitale et al. (2020)]. Automotive manufacturers might find it hard in the near future to take full responsibility of a vehicle's production as the emerging technologies are adding to the complexity of the final, now sophisticated, product. Therefore, more partnerships will arise between OEMs themselves or with other entities, working together towards improving the experience and safety of road users. The European and American OEMs must realign their strategies to reduce the industry's dependency on Asian suppliers. Component shortage together with significant price increase of raw materials and electricity will lead to higher production costs. The automotive sector will slowly follow the path of tech giants, with businesses emerging as technological leaders in various specialties and occasionally establishing standards in the industry [Hensley et al. (2022)]. The shifting demand of the consumers is obliging OEMs to focus on alternative solutions to conventional vehicle ownership such as vehicle subscription services but also to strengthen their business model in the B2B market.

References

Accenture

2020

"The automotive experience reimaged" Accenture

Brown D., Flickenschild M., Mazzo C., Gasparotti A., Panagiotidou Z., Dingemane J., and Bratzel S.

2021

"The Future of the EU Automotive Sector" Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies

Burkacky O., Deichmann J., Pfingstag P., and Werra J.

2022

"Semiconductor shortage: How the automotive industry can succeed" McKinsey Semiconductors Practice

Burkacky O., Lingemann S., Möller T., and Pototzky K.

2021

"Coping with the auto-semiconductor shortage: Strategies for success" McKinsey Automotive & Assembly Practice

Hausler S., Heineke K., Hensley R., Möller T., Schwedhelm D., and Shen P.

2020

"The impact of COVID-19 on future mobility solutions?" McKinsey Center for Future Mobility

Heineke K., Kampshoff P., Möller T., and Schwedhelm D.

2021

"Mobility's rebound: An industry recovers, but where is it heading?" McKinsey Center for Future Mobility

Heineke K., Kampshoff P., Möller T., and Wu T.

2020

"From no mobility to future mobility: Where COVID-19 has accelerated change" McKinsey Center for Future Mobility Compendium 2020–21

Hensley R., Laczkowski K., Möller T., and Schwedhelm D.

2022

"Can the automotive industry scale fast enough?" McKinsey & Company

Kaas H. W., Mohr D., Gao P., Müller P. and other McKinsey & Company authors

2016

"Automotive revolution – perspective towards 2030" McKinsey & Company

Levy Y.

2022

"Global Automotive Cybersecurity Report" Upstream Security

Proff H., Kunsch M., Walker A. and other Deloitte authors.

2022

"2022 Global Automotive Consumer Study" Deloitte Development LLC

Schellong D., Sadek P., Lang N., and Mattson M.

2021

"Will Car Subscriptions Revolutionize Auto Sales?" BCG's Center for Mobility Innovation

Vitale J., Bowman K., and Robinson R.

2020

"How the pandemic is changing the future of automotive" The Deloitte Consumer Industry Center